

Some New Observations on the Friedel-Crafts Reaction*

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In connection with some other work, it was necessary to prepare a large quantity of β -resorecylanilide, or 2:4-dihydroxybenzanilide which was prepared by V. N. Byatnal and R. D. Desai¹ by a long process. It was thought that the easiest and cheapest method would be the condensation of resorcinol with phenylisocyanate, in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. However, when the reaction was carried out, it was found that instead of the nuclear hydrogen, the hydrogen of the hydroxyl group reacted either in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride or in its absence. But phenylisothiocyanate reacted with resorcinol in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride giving 2:4-dihydroxythiobenzenilide. This striking difference between the behaviour of phenylisocyanate, and phenylisothiocyanate prompted us to study this reaction in greater details with some aromatic hydrocarbons, mono- and dihydric phenols, and mono-, and diamino-anthraquinones.

The condensation of phenylisocyanate with aromatic hydrocarbons in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride with the formation of aromatic anilides was studied in 1885 by Leuckart². The same investigator found that the homologues of benzene, as well as their substituted derivatives reacted in the same manner with the insertion of the anilido group-CONH-C₆H₅. The usual rule of substitution was obeyed by this reaction. In the same year Leuckart and Schmidt³ reported that phenylisocyanate reacted with phenol ethers to yield *p*-methoxybenzanilides in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. Small quantities of aromatic hydroxy-anilides were also formed due to the demethylating action of anhydrous aluminium chloride. Similarly according to Gattermann⁴, phenylisothiocyanate reacted with aromatic hydrocarbons in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride with the formation of aryl thioanilides. According to Toost and Gattermann⁵, phenylisothiocyanate condensed with phenolic ethers in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride to give methoxy-thiobenzenilides. Gattermann⁶ condensed resorcinol diethylether with phenylisothiocyanate obtaining 2:4-diethoxy-thiobenzenilide. According to F. Meyer and A. Manbour⁷, phenol and α -naphthol condensed with phenylisothioxyanate. R. Rivier and Kunz⁸ condensed *o*-, *m* and *p*-cresols, as well as resorcinol, phloro-

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5. R. Toost and L. Gattermann, *Ber*, 1892, **25**, 3528.
6. L. Gatterman, *Loc. cit.*
7. F. Meyer and A. Manbour, *Ber*, 1929, **62**, 1921.
8. R. Rivier and S. Kunz, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1932, **15**, 376.

glucinol, α -naphthol and β -naphthol with phenyl isothiocyanate in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. K. K. Jinwala and J. P. Trivedi⁹ have condensed *p*-anisyl- and *p*-tolylisothiocyanates with benzene, anisole, phenol, *o*- and *p*-chlorophenols, *p*-nitrophenol, quinol, resorcinol and naphthols. They found that among the Lewis acids, aluminium chloride was the most efficient catalyst, while best yields with this catalyst were obtained using carbondisulphide as the solvent. F. Effenberger and R. Gleiter^{9a} have recently condensed *p*-chlorophenylisocyanate, ethylisocyanate, and *p*-toluene-sulphonylisocyanate with benzene and its derivatives.

In the present work, benzene, naphthalene, anthracene, phenanthrene, phenol, anisole, resorcinol, resorcinol-dimethylether, resacetophenone, and 7 hydroxy-4-methyl-coumarin have been condensed with phenylisocyanate, in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride using nitrobenzene as the solvent. Besides the above mentioned compounds, orcinol and phloroglucinol have been condensed with phenylisothiocyanate under identical conditions. The ratio of phenylisothiocyanate and the catalyst was 1:2, while the amount of the solvent was in the ratio of 1:20. The results obtained are as follows:—

Benzene gave benzanilide with phenylisocyanate, while *naphthalene* gave mainly the anilide of 1-naphthioic acid¹⁰ (95 percent) together with a small amount of the isomeric anilide of 2-naphthioic acid¹¹ (5 percent). *Anthracene* gave a mixture of the anilides of anthracene-2-carboxylic acid¹², anthracene-1 carboxylic acid^{13,14}, and anthracene 9-carboxylic acid^{15,16}. *Phenanthrene* gave a mixture of the anilides of phenanthrene-2-carboxylic acid^{17,18} and phenanthrene -9-carboxylic acid^{17,19,20}.

Phenol condensed with phenylisocyanate either in presence or absence of aluminium chloride giving the phenyl ester of phenylcarbamic acid; *Anisole* gave the anilide of *p*-methoxybenzoic acid²¹. *Resorcinol*, either in presence or absence of anhydrous aluminium chloride gave a neutral product which was the diurethane, and an acidic product which was the monourethane. *Resorcinol dimethyl ether* gave the anilide of 2:4-dimethoxy-benzoic acid, which on demethylation with 48 percent hydriodic acid gave 2:4-dihydroxybenzanilide²². Resorcinol dimethyl ether reacted with two moles of phenylisocyanate giving the dianilide of 4:6-dimethoxyisophthalic acid. *Resacetophenone* reacted with two moles of phenylisocyanate giving a neutral product which was the 4-acetyl-*m*-phenylene ester of phenylcarbamic acid. 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-coumarin gave a neutral product which was the 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-coumarinyl ester of phenylcarbamic acid.

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9. A. F. Effenberger and Gleiter, *Ber.*, 1954, **67** (2), 472.
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22. V. N. Byatnal and R. D. Desai, *Loc. cit.*

Benzene reacted with phenylisothiocyanate in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride giving thiobenzanilide. *Naphthalene* gave a mixture of the anilides of 2-thionaphthoic acid (3 parts) and 1-thionaphthoic acid (1 part). *Anthracene* reacted with phenylisothiocyanate giving a mixture of the thioanilides of anthracene-2-carboxylic acid (2 parts) and anthracene-1-carboxylic acid (1 part). *Phenanthrene* gave the thioanilide of phenanthrenyl-2-carboxylic acid.

Phenol underwent nuclear condensation with phenylisothiocyanate giving the thioanilide of *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid, while *anisole* gave *p*-methoxy-thiobenzanilide. *Resorcinol* underwent nuclear condensation with one mole of phenylisothiocyanate giving β -resorcylthioanilide. *Orcinol* reacted with one mole of phenylisothiocyanate giving a mixture of the thioanilides of β -orsellinic acid^{23,24} and ν orsellinic acid.^{25,26} Thus, orcinol underwent simultaneous β - and γ -substitution in its reaction with phenylisothiocyanate in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. Instance of such exclusive β -substitutions or simultaneous β - and γ -substitutions in the derivatives of resorcinol and orcinol have been observed in the past by Baker and Co-workers²⁷, Shah and Co-workers²⁸ and Desai and Co-workers²⁹.

Phloroglucinol gave the thioanilide of 2:4:6-trihydroxy-benzoic acid^{30,31}. *Resacetophnone* gave a mixture of the thioanilides of 2:4-dihydroxy-5-acetyl-benzoic acid³² and 2:6-dihydroxy-3-acetyl benzoic acid³³. Here again, there was simultaneous β - and γ -substitution. *7-hydroxy-4-methyl-coumarin* reacted with one mole of phenylisothiocyanate giving the 6-thiocarbacylido- and 8-thiocarbanilido-derivatives of 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin. Here also there was the simultaneous β - and ν -substitution.

Phenylisocyanate reacted with 1-amino- and 2-aminoanthraquinones very slowly even at 130-140°, but it was found that anhydrous aluminium chloride acted as a very efficient catalyst to activate the hydrogen of the amino group, and facilitated the formation of phenylanthraquinonyl ureas. Thus 1-amino- and 2-amino anthraquinones reacted with an equimolecular quantity of phenylisocyanate in presence of one and a half mole of anhydrous aluminium chloride at 100° with the formation of 1-phenylcarbamide- and 2-phenylcarbamide-anthraquinones. Their acid hydrolysis to amino-anthraquinones as well as their I. R. spectra proved their structure to be anthraquinonyl ureas. 1,4-diaminoanthraquinone reacted with one and two moles of phenylisocyanate giving respectively 4-amino-1-(phenylcarbamide)-anthraquinone and 1:4-di-(phenylcarbamide)-anthraquinone. 1:5-diaminoanthraquinone gave with one and two moles of phenylisocyanate, 5-amino-1-(phenylcarbamide)-anthraquinone and 1:5 di-(phenylcarbamide)-anthraquinone respectively.

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27. W. Baker and Co-workers, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1684; 1935, 628; 1936, 274; 1937, 479.

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Similarly 2:6 *diaminoanthraquinone* reacted with one and two moles of phenylisocyanate, giving 6-amino-2-(phenylcarbamido)-anthraquinone, and 2:6-di-(phenylcarbamido)-anthraquinone respectively in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride.

Phenylisothiocyanate was found to be very sluggish in reacting with 1-aminoanthraquinone even at 160°, but in presence of one and a half mole of anhydrous aluminium chloride, the reaction went very smoothly at 100°. Thus 1-amino- and 2-aminoanthraquinones reacted with phenylisothiocyanate giving respectively 1-(phenylthiocarbamido)- and 2-(phenylthiocarbamido)-anthraquinones. 1:4 *diaminoanthraquinone* reacted with one and two moles of phenylisothiocyanate giving 4-amino-1-(phenylthiocarbamido)anthraquinone and 1:4-di-(phenylthiocarbamido)-anthraquinone respectively. 1:5- and 2:6-*diaminoanthraquinones* reacted similarly giving their respective phenylthiourea derivatives. *m*-tolylisothiocyanate also underwent the similar type of reactions, though much less slowly. Acylation of amino-anthraquinones with acid anhydrides and acid chlorides requires a fairly high temperature (160°), but in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride this reaction goes very smoothly on the water-bath.

With the exception of the dyestuff obtained from 1-aminoanthraquinone and phenylisocyanate, all other anthraquinonylphenylureas and phenylthioureas are good vat dyes, and dye best by the I. N. Method. The shades on dyed cotton range from yellow to orange and reddish violet, but there are no blue, green and black shades. The levelling properties are good and the fastness to chlorine as well as to light is 4-5. They vat easily requiring only a small quantity of caustic soda and the addition of common salt is necessary for the exhaustion of the bath. The substitution of oxygen by sulphur leads to the deepening of shades on dyed cotton.

In an unsuccessful attempt to condense phenylisocyanate with anthraquinone in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride dissolved in nitrobenzene, it was noticed that a blue-black powder which had the property of a vat dyestuff was obtained. A systematic examination of this complex reaction showed that the powder was a mixture of four substances (one of them unvattable). Surprisingly, each dyestuff contained a good percentage of nitrogen and chlorine. No information on the structure of these dyestuffs could be obtained from infrared absorption spectra in nujol as the spectrum of only nujol was obtained in each case. Chromatographic separation gave four products A, B, C₁ and C₂, which dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid giving blue-black colour and the original products could be recovered on diluting the solutions with water. The quantitative estimation of C, H, N, and chlorine responded to the formula C₆₄H₃₄O₂N₆Cl₆ (A), C₅₂H₂₄O₂N₄Cl₄ (B), C₄₀H₁₄O₂N₂Cl₂ (C₁), and C₆₄H₃₂O₂N₆Cl₆ (C₂). The mechanism of the formation of these dyestuffs may be visualised as follows:—

The first step in the formation of these dyestuffs is the Scholl³⁴ condensation of anthraquinone to 1:1-dianthraquinonyl in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. The hydrogen evolved during this condensation reduces nitrobenzene to various products like nitrosobenzene, hydroxylamine and aniline. All these products take part in the reaction at one stage or the other. The dianthraquinonyl also undergoes reduction to dianthrone, which during the course of the reaction gets converted to *ms*-naphthodianthrone in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride according to Scholl and Mansfield³⁵. The

34. R. Scholl and Co-workers, *Ber.*, 1910, **43**, 2202.

35. R. Scholl and J. Mansfield, *Ber.*, 1910, **43**, 1739.

nitrogen content of the dyestuffs arises from the condensation of either nitrosobenzene, or hydroxylamine or aniline at the reactive centres which are provided by the α - and β -positions, as well as the keto groups of the anthraquinone moiety. Moreover, two carbazole rings are also formed, along with the formation of the *ms*-naphtho-dianthrone ring. These reactions are favoured by the high temperature of the reaction (160-180°) and the condensing capacity of anhydrous aluminium chloride. The chlorination of the resulting dyestuffs is due to the nascent-chlorine obtained by the oxidation of hydrogen chloride by nitrobenzene at the high temperature of the reaction. Thus, the formation of the dyestuffs, A, B, C₁, and C₂ can probably be visualised as under. The simplest of them all in composition is the dyestuff (C₁) C₄₀H₁₄O₂N₂Cl₄ which is probably formed thus:—

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

The *dyestuff* (C_2) differs from (C_1) in having four more nitrogen atoms, which are introduced through the condensation of either nitrosobenzene or hydroxylamine at the four α -positions and two more chlorine atoms. Its formula is $C_{64}H_{32}O_2N_6Cl_6$ and its formation from (C_1) can be visualised thus:—

The *dyestuff* (A) is the leuco compound of the dyestuff (C_2) and the reduction of the vat dyestuff (C_2) takes place due to the hydrogen liberated during the reaction. The *dyestuff* (B) is unvattable and its formula is $C_{64}H_{34}N_6Cl_4$. Its structure can be visualised from the dyestuff (C_1) as under:—

FIG. 3

The dyestuffs A, C_1 and C_2 vat easily and dye cotton by the I. N. Method giving shades which are bluish-gray, and reddish-gray, and their fastness to chlorine as well as light is 4-5. A similar type of reaction is given by β -methylantraquinone, β -chloroantraquinone and benzanthrone, and we are busy studying it.

In continuation of our work on the meagrely studied Fries migration of the aryl esters of aryl sulphonates, we extended it to the esters of α - and β -naphthylsulphonic acids, *p*-chloro, *p*-bromo- and *p*-methoxy-benzene-sulphonic acids, with a view to providing a convenient method for the synthesis of hydroxydiaryl sulphones which are useful as anti-septics and dyestuff intermediates. A comparison with the analogous work on the Fries migration of the aryl esters of carboxylic acids has brought into prominence certain striking differences. They are (a) the Fries migration of the aryl esters of alkylsulphonic acids does not take place, (b) the arylsulphonates require higher temperatures for rearrangement than the arylcarboxylates, (c) the aryl esters of α -naphthylsulphonic acid gave ortho-substitution, whereas those of β -naphthylsulphonic acid yielded para-substitution, (d) the nature of the substitution during the migration was usually more unpredictable in the case of the arylsulphonates than in that of arylcarboxylates. Therefore, evidence for the structure of resulting products had to be obtained by authentic synthesis, which was not always easy, (e) evidence of β - and γ -substitution in the derivatives of resorcinol³⁷ could be obtained in appropriate cases, and this part of the problem requires further investiga-

36. J. C. Amin and R. D. Desai, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1954, **133**, 181, J. C. Amin, Ph.D. Thesis, Gujarat University, 1954.

37. Miss M. D. Bhavsar and R. D. Desai, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **31**, 167.

tion, (f) a study of the ultra-violet spectra of hydroxy-sulphones by Baliah and co-workers³⁸ has been very useful in deciding the nature of the migration i.e. whether orth. or para.

The investigations described in the foregoing pages were carried out in collaboration with Miss S. K. Dalal³⁹ (now Mrs S. S. Palkhiwala) and A. R. Parikh⁴⁰ to whom my sincere thanks are due, for their devotion, diligence, and persistence.

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38. V. Baliah and A. Mathew, *Ibid.*, 1957, **34**, 365.

39. Miss S. K. Dalal, Ph. D. Thesis, Gujarat University, 1966.

40. A. R. Parikh, Ph. D. Thesis, Gujarat University, 1966.